

E-Storybooks as Supplementary Material for Fourth Grade Elementary School Students

Luh Dewi Asih^{1*}, G.A.P. Suprianti^{2*}, Luh Gede Eka Wahyuni³

^{1,2,3} English Language Education Department, Universitas Pendidikan Ganesha, Singaraja, Indonesia

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ABSTRAK

Sumber materi pembelajaran bahasa Inggris yang digunakan di sekolah hanya berupa buku teks tanpa ada bahan pelengkap. Materi pelengkap dalam proses belajar mengajar bahasa Inggris dianggap sebagai salah satu cara untuk melibatkan siswa dalam belajar. Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk mengembangkan e-storybook untuk siswa kelas IV sebagai bahan pelengkap berdasarkan Kurikulum Merdeka. Penelitian *Design and Development* ini menggunakan model ADDE seperti yang dikemukakan oleh Richey dan Klein (2014). Pendekatan kualitatif dan kuantitatif digunakan untuk menganalisis data non numerik dan numerik secara berurutan. Guru bahasa Inggris dan siswa kelas empat dilibatkan sebagai subjek penelitian ini. Pakar dan pengguna yang memvalidasi e-storybook memberikan skor keseluruhan sebesar 5 yang menunjukkan e-storybook yang dikembangkan merupakan "Produk Unggulan" dan valid untuk digunakan. Oleh karena itu, e-storybook yang dikembangkan dapat digunakan oleh siswa kelas empat untuk belajar bahasa Inggris dengan cara yang menyenangkan dan interaktif. Karena buku cerita elektronik ini memiliki berbagai komponen yang sesuai dengan kebutuhan siswa dan kurikulum saat ini, guru disarankan untuk menggunakannya sebagai bahan tambahan dalam proses belajar mengajar bahasa Inggris.

ABSTRACT

The source of English learning materials used at school was only textbook without any supplementary materials. Supplementary materials in English teaching and learning process are considered as one of the ways to engage students in learning. This study aims to develop e-storybooks for fourth-grade pupils as supplementary materials based on the Merdeka curriculum. This Design and Development study used the ADDE model as proposed by Richey and Klein (2014). Qualitative and quantitative approach were used to analyze both non numerical and numerical data sequentially. English teacher and grade four students were involved as the subject of this study. Experts and user who validated the e-storybooks gave an overall score of 5 that showed the developed e-storybooks was the "Excellent Product" and valid to be used. Therefore, the developed e-storybooks can be used by grade four students to learn English in fun and interactive way. As these e-storybooks have various components that match to the students' needs and the current curriculum, teacher was suggested to utilize it as the supplementary materials in English teaching and learning process..

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1. INTRODUCTION

English is a means of communication used throughout the world. Thus, the term of 'international' language is attached to this language. Most of people use English in various activities and for some intentions (Raja et al., 2022; Winaldo & Oktaviani, 2022). It is also known that, English has become the top foreign language learned in the world (Rahman & Saputra, 2021; Yulfi & Syaprizal, 2020). This same situation also occurs in Indonesia. Both formal and informal educational settings offer English as a foreign language instruction. Strengthened by the implementation Merdeka Curriculum as the used curriculum, English is placed as a compulsory subject taught in all grades start from primary schools until senior high schools. Those learners in primary schools are basically children that have been often concerned when it comes to English teaching. Teaching English to young learners is not simple as it can be challenging and provide opportunity at the same time (Suprianti et al., 2024; Wulandari et al., 2020). Children often get bored easily and they have limited attention span but they learn new language easier than adult (Cahyati et al., 2019; Suprianti & Jayanta, 2020). Furthermore, children these days are also regarded as digital natives. It indicates that they have incorporated digital technology into their everyday routines (Smith et al., 2020; Suprianti et al., 2024). If children use their phones, laptops, and other devices for activities, they will be more motivated. The existence of supplementary

material can cope with the characteristics of children so that the students engage in learning and the interactivity is achieved (Bajrami, 2020; Pujiani et al., 2023).

The learning activities suggested for children consist of games, songs, role plays, and storytelling (Hadiyanti & Yolanda, 2021; Pujiani et al., 2022). Supplementary materials were very important in English learning process. It can keep maintaining the students' interest and attention in learning and also help them to understand complex materials (Bajrami, 2020; Pujiani et al., 2022). Supplementary materials also can activate and engage the students in learning process so that it becomes one important thing in the learning process (Cherrez et al., 2018; Giguashvili & Sanaia, 2023). Unfortunately, the demand of Merdeka curriculum to achieve the interactivity in learning are not well achieve because there is no supplementary materials in the learning process. This was seen from observation done by the researcher in an English class. The teaching method and resources used being observed in this case. It was found that the teaching method and the resources have not been tailored to the students need and interest. The monotonous use of textbooks, which are less visually appealing resulted to sufficiently hard for pupils to understand. Additionally, it is not connected with digital technology, as evidenced by the absence of digital books or learning resources. It results in teacher-centered learning. However, teacher also faced challenges in creating supplementary materials that technologically integrated, meet the needs of the students, and adhere to the curriculum. It is caused by the teacher's incompetence as well as time constraints. Seeing that situation, a supplementary material is needed. The current study created an e-storybook as a supplementary material to aid teachers and students in the process of learning English based on that phenomena. A particular kind of book called a storybook is used to represent a story that has characters, a plot, a conflict, text and illustrations to deliver message (Hüseyin & Balci, 2016; Ratminingsih & Budasi, 2018). It supports the growth of the pupils' imaginations and their ability to visualize the events in the story. Students are able to experience the identical circumstances as those described in the story (Lubaale et al., 2021; Ratminingsih et al., 2020).

Additionally, it is accompanied by images that make it simpler for kids to understand the essence of the story. As this e-storybook is an electronic book, it also integrated technologies. Several benefits associated with using e-storybooks in the process of teaching and learning. First, as e-storybooks are portable, learning can be facilitated anywhere at anytime. Second, users receive a great deal more than printed books. Third, it can be hyper-linked to other sources and is less expensive than printed books. Fourth, readers can quickly and easily access e-books. Fifth, e-storybooks provide a number of interactive activities that allow students and teacher to connect with one another (Anderson & Dron, 2011; Giguashvili & Sanaia, 2023; Lieung et al., 2021). By using e-storybook in the teaching and learning process, it is hoped that it can create an effective and interactive learning process that is in line with the curriculum and needs of students. The application of e-storybooks for education were also covered in a number of earlier studies. The interactive storybooks for ecoliteration instruction were developed in an effort to gain primary school pupils' interest in reading on non-English topics (Hendratno et al., 2022; Suhardiana & Lestari, 2020). The results demonstrate that the pupils' learning outcomes are considerably enhanced by the use of interactive storybooks. Research on the effect of using e-storybook and storytelling techniques also conducted and the result shown it helped to increase students' interest in learning English. Besides, research on the use of storybooks based on local culture to teach English to young learners was also carried out (Pujiani et al., 2022; Ratminingsih & Budasi, 2018). The result revealed the advantages and positive impact of employing e-storybooks for learning process. Those previous study involved storybook that only uses pictures, stories, and audio without any exercises to assess students' comprehension of the material. On the other hand, the storybooks mentioned in the previous studies were not align with the current curriculum namely Merdeka curriculum.

Based on that gaps, the current study concentrated on creating e-storybooks to be used in English classes for grade 4 students at a primary school in Buleleng. The novelty of this study is e-storybooks were created based on Merdeka curriculum as a guide with follow up interactive activities. This study aims to develop e-storybooks for fourth-grade pupils as supplementary materials based on the Merdeka curriculum. It was expected that by employing stories to enhance interactive learning activities, these e-storybooks would serve as supplementary materials that helps students in learning English and to master language skills.

2. METHOD

This study used Design & Development (D&D) method (Erfani, 2019). ADDE model was used to create the current e-storybooks. ADDE stands for Analysis, Design, Development, and Evaluation successively. This study was conducted at a school in Buleleng namely SD Negeri 1 Suwug. Three reasons were taken into consideration in choosing the research setting such as, the school has implemented Merdeka Curriculum, it integrated technology in the learning process supported with the existence of tools such as Chromebook and LCD projector, and the school has limited number of English source such as books or supplementary materials. The English teacher and grade four students of SD Negeri 1 Suwug were participated in this research. Four

instruments were involved in collecting the data namely observation sheet, interview guides, expert judgment sheet, and user judgment sheet. Construct validity were done to validate those instruments so that the instruments were ready to be used. It was validated by the experts before being used in collecting the data. The result of validation from the experts were analyzed by using Gregory formula. After the instruments deemed as valid to be used, the researcher started to collect data through several stages. In analysis, the researcher conducted three activities such as doing an observation of the classroom learning process on English subject, analyzing syllabus and learning materials, and interviewing teacher and students. Design as the second phase was prepared to begin the construct of blueprint for the e-storybooks based on the analytical results. Subsequently, the blueprint was turned into developing product prototype during the development stage. Before the final prototype was put to use, experts evaluated it to determine its quality by using expert judgment sheet. The result of expert judgment was further analyzed in both quantitative and qualitative manners. The last but not least stage was evaluation, when the user (teacher) assessed the final product after being used in an English language learning of grade four by using user judgment sheet that should be filled by teacher and also interviewing the teacher and grade four students. The data collected were analyzed qualitatively for non numerical data and quantitatively for numerical data.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result

The first research question was asked about the development of e-storybooks for grade four students. The e-storybooks were developed by using ADDE model. The steps included analysis, design, development, and evaluation successively. Three major activities were covered in the analysis phase, namely observation, document analysis and interviews. Those three intended to analyze the needs of students in the learning activities and was used as the foundation to develop e-storybooks as supplementary materials. The observation was done in learning process of English subject for grade four to gain data about the teaching and learning activities. The observation sheet was used in obtaining the data. The use of e-storybooks and learning process itself were the concern of the observation. As observed, the teacher used English textbook in the learning process as the source of learning materials provided by The Ministry of Education, Culture, Research, and Technology. However, there was no other application of e-storybooks or materials integrated with Merdeka Belajar curriculum. Thus, it can be concluded that the only material used to teach was the textbook. In the learning process on the other hand, the researcher focused on methods and media used, interactions during learning, and student responses during learning. It was observed that the learning process still uses the teacher-centered learning. It means that there was no interactivity between teacher and students. The students were not active in responding several questions asked by the teacher. They showed disinterest in the learning process. It even led students inactive as the teaching material used was only textbook that emerged as to monotonous learning activities. The absence of integration of technology was also seen in the observation which is still conventional. Seeing the phenomena, it was concluded that innovation and creativity were needed. Supplementary materials in the form of e-storybooks could be the solution for the problem. As it integrates technology, it can motivate and engage students in learning. Therefore, the development of e-storybooks as supplementary materials based on Merdeka curriculum are needed in the teaching and learning English in grade four.

In the interview, teacher said that he was very interested in the development of e-storybook as supplementary materials in English teaching and learning process. Teacher thought that e-storybooks integrated with Merdeka Belajar can support the learning process to be more effective as well as enhance students' motivation and engagement in learning. Moreover, teacher expected that the e-storybook contain pictures and also audios to give real example of how to pronounce the text and also contain with exercise that can practice their language skills. On the other hand, in the interview conducted with some students, they said that they faced difficulties in comprehending the materials from the textbook without assisted by teacher. They added, the frequent use of textbook was boring. They expected that the learning process become more fun and interactive by applying pictures and audios. Last but not least, they also said that the use technology in learning motivates them in learning. Based on the analysis of the syllabus used, four language skills, namely Listening, Reading, Speaking, and Writing are expected to be mastered by the students. In addition, there are also learning objectives and language focus that the teacher can use as a reference in making teaching plans. However, the learning activities planned in the teaching module are not in line with the syllabus. For example, when it emphasized on students' speaking skill, the learning activities should be interactive. It means there should be interaction between students. If additional materials supporting this interactive activity are available, they can be used. In addition to analyzing the teaching module and syllabus, the researcher analyzed the textbook to identify the subject matter for the e-storybooks. Teachers were involved in choosing subjects because they are aware of the needs of their pupils and want the e-storybook to be built with his students' needs. The chosen topics included Preposition of Place, Time, Daily Activities, and Adverbs of Frequency. Once the researcher finished doing the

activities in analysis phase, it was continued to the design phase. The blueprint of the e-storybooks was designed as the guidance in making the prototype of e-storybooks in the development phase. Microsoft Word was used to create the book content, meanwhile Canva and Procreate application were used to create the illustrations that would be put in the e-storybooks. The blueprint consisted of topic, learning objectives, language skills, and the activities. The storyline of e-storybooks was made based on the previous learning topics chosen. The chosen topics were “My Living Room is Beside the Kitchen” (Preposition of Place), “Be On Time!” (Time), “I Go to School After Having Breakfast” (Daily Activities), “He Always Gets Up at 6 O'clock” (Adverbs of Frequency). After selecting the topics for e-storybooks development, the blueprint of e-storybooks was started to be designed. The example of blueprint can be seen in [Table 1](#).

Table 1. Example of Blueprint

Topics	Learning Objectives	Language Skills	Activities
My Living Room is Beside the Kitchen (Preposition of Place)	1. Students are able to identify prepositions	Reading, Listening, Writing and Speaking	Pre-activity: 1. Students look at the picture provided that shows the position of rooms at house. 2. Several pictures and vocabularies about preposition of place will be provided to introduce the words to students with the audio. Students have to listen and repeat the audio. Whilst activity: 3. Students have to read the story and listen to the audio. 4. Students have to do an individual task like fill in the blank.

The three types of activities found in the e-storybooks were pre-activities, whilst-activities, and post-activities. The purpose of the pre-activity was to get the students ready for the tasks that were more challenging. Students used it as a brainstorming exercise and to refresh their memories of prior material. Afterwards, there would be a whilst activity consisting of multiple tasks including listening and reading the stories, independent, pair, or group work. Not to be forgotten is the post-activity. Usually, it takes the form of a task that can be measured so that the instructor can use it to assess the students. The development phase included the process of creating prototypes of e-storybooks. Blueprint as the basis for developing the prototype was used to create the prototypes. There were three major parts of the development process such as drafting the prototypes, revising the prototypes, and finalizing the prototypes. In the drafting process, characters of the story were firstly made by using "Procreate" software application. The process included drawing the sketch of characters and other supporting elements. Once the sketches were done into pictures, the layout drafting process was begun. Canva application was used as it facilitated the researcher to customize the layout for e-storybooks. Adding pictures, audios, and text for the activities in the e-storybooks were completed. After the drafting process was completed, the process of revising prototypes were started. The completed e-storybooks were then ready to be revised in this phase. Several valuable suggestions and advice concerning the design of the e-storybook and more importantly the content of the books were obtained. The e-storybooks was revised as suggested previously. Some revisions can be seen in [Table 2](#).

Table 2. Revision of the E-storybook

Aspects	Before Revision	After Revision
Title of the topic	“Fun Group Work”	“The Toilet is Next to The Kitchen”.
Picture	One picture was not enough	Four more pictures were added
Grammar	“After school, Doni, Joni, and Dayu go to Dita’s house together”	“After school, Doni, Joni, and Dayu went to Dita’s house together”
Direct quotation	“Dita tells Doni that the toilet is next to the kitchen”	“the toilet is next to the kitchen”

Once the revision was done, the process moved into finalizing the prototypes. Finalizing process included providing the final result of the product after doing some revision. The final product was then ready to be validated by the experts. The e-storybooks, as the product consisted of opening, pre activity, whilst activity, post activity, and closing. [Table 3](#) QR codes show the final product of the e-storybooks.

Table 3. The Developed E-Storybooks

E-storybooks	QR Codes

Base on [Table 3](#), the final products provided above were then evaluated by two experts. It was done to assess the quality of the e-storybooks before being tried out at school. The data distribution of the expert judgment result can be seen in [Figure 1](#).

Figure 1. The Data Distribution of Expert Judgment Result

It can be seen from [Figure 1](#), expert 1 gave a score 4 on three aspects and 5 on five aspects. Meanwhile expert 2 gave a score 4 on 2 aspects and 5 on six aspects. After obtaining those results, the researcher calculated the value mode to determine the quality of the product seen from expert validation. [Table 4](#) shows the mode score of the result of expert validation.

Table 4. The Mode Score of Expert Judgment Result

Num.	Judges	Mode score	Conclusion
1	Expert 1	5	Excellent product
2	Expert 2	5	Excellent product

Table 4, it can be seen that the mode score showed 5 on both expert validation, which means that the e-storybooks were categorized as excellent products. The developed e-storybooks have followed the required criteria as stated in each aspect of the expert judgment sheet and were ready to be used. The evaluation stage is the final step in creating an e-storybook. In this phase, the second research question that asked about the quality of developed e-storybooks were answered. In order to evaluate the created e-storybook's practicability and accessibility, the researcher conducted a small group trial at this stage. This small group trial involved grade 4 students. Following up on this small-group try out, four students were interviewed. They were selected to speak as the representative of the pupils and share their opinions about the e-storybook that has been tried. Besides that, researcher also conducted user judgment. Teacher were asked to fill the judgment based on the e-storybook being developed. In addition to interviewing students to gather their comments, the researcher also interviewed the teacher. The purpose of the interview process was to find out what teachers thought of the e-storybook. The outcome of the teacher and student interviews served as the basis for the assessment of the e-storybook's quality.

The teacher participated in the user judgment. First, an e-storybook was used to conduct an English language learning tryout. Subsequently, the English teacher was requested to fill out the user judgment sheet in order to score the quality of the created e-storybook. The eight aspects on the user judgment sheet were rated as follows: 1 (poor), 2 (below average), 3 (average), 4 (good), and 5 (excellent). The user judgment revealed that the teacher gave scale of 4 on 1 point and scale of 5 on 7 points. In order to assess the quality of the e-storybook being developed, the researcher additionally calculated the mode score after received the results of the user judgment. The result of calculation revealed that the mode score was "5" which indicated "excellent." Consequently, it can be said that the created e-storybook was of excellent quality.

According to the results of the teacher interview, the created e-storybook had an eye-catching, straightforward layout with easy-to-follow instructions, making it a simpler tool to use. The units covered in this e-storybook and the interactive activities included show how well it aligned with the Merdeka curriculum and the learning objectives. The teacher also mentioned that, as students quickly disinterested in learning just on handbooks, this e-storybook can serve as an additional materials. The activities in this e-storybook were also appropriate for the children' cognitive levels, making it easy for them to understand. The most considerably good media is designed systematically which can motivate students to learn, simple and easy to operate, and more importantly reliable and valid. The teacher expected that the e-storybook would be beneficial to the students, particularly in terms of motivate and engage them in learning English. Besides interviewing the teacher, the representative students also expressed their opinions regarding the use of e-storybooks in English classes. They expressed how excited they were to use this e-storybook. They enjoyed the activities as well as the design and material, which included images, stories, audio, and stories. The images were fascinating. They were also provided with further information from the school handbook. Students also mentioned that utilizing this e-storybook made them feel happy to learn and that it could be understood, interesting, and helpful.

Discussion

Based on the result of this study, a few things can be discussed. The created e-storybook was utilized as supplementary materials that met the needs of students because the textbook was not enough to develop students' language competence (Nurliana, 2019; Wahyuni & Tantri, 2020). According to several related previous study, the e-storybooks are helpful in encouraging vocabulary growth and an understanding of language structure (Dhirapriyani et al., 2024; Hsieh et al., 2011). In the current study, certain words in the developed e-storybooks were highlighted to make it easier for student to identify the words related to the topic so that they can obtain more vocabularies exposure. The presence of images that are connected to the text can serve as a medium for aiding students in comprehending the narrative as well as understanding complex materials (Pujiani et al., 2022; Suhardiana & Lestari, 2020). Students are attracted by the colorful pictures and design, which aids in keeping their focus while reading. This e-storybook's layout and content are certain to encourage pupils to read since it includes engaging illustrations such as pictures that relate to their daily lives. Straightforward language and instructions were also offered in this e-storybook by involving simple words that was easy to be understood. The audio inserted in this e-storybook also provided real example to pronounce the words. Several studies argued that the listening while reading activity fosters the development of the students' language skills. Listening while reading was effective to enhance their language skills (Asrimawati & Margana, 2020; Tangkakarn, 2020). Therefore, this e-storybook surely attracted and helped the students to learn.

Previous study argued about the presence of interactive learning activities can encourage and engage the students in the learning process (Rizal et al., 2024; Wahyuni & Pratiwi, 2021). The developed e-storybooks supported interactivity in learning through follow up activities that was involved. Matching, fill-in-the-blank, reading and listening to stories, and information gap exercises are examples of interactive activities in this e-storybook. Moreover, several studies also stated that internet has been part of students life so that they can access materials everywhere and everytime. Therefore, students need a media that support the learning activities both in the school hours and outside the classroom that can motivate them to learn (Pujiani et al., 2023; Suprianti et al., 2020; Suprianti, 2020). The developed e-storybooks provided an opportunity for students to learn everywhere and everytime. It was because this book in the form of electronic book which give an opportunity for students to learn English even they were not in the classroom. Students can access the e-storybook through their smartphone or laptop by scanning the barcode of each e-storybook and learn English. Based on the features and contents in this e-storybooks, it would be beneficial for students as a supplementary materials that was attractive, interactive, and engage them in learning. Interactive follow up activities as the new thing in this e-storybooks development would be helpful to encourage and engage students in learning and boost their language skills. Besides its beneficial features, there were a few limitations on the e-storybook being created in this study. The audio cannot be played when it is converted to PDF or another format and only can be played in Canva. Because this e-storybook performed better on Canva, it can only be accessed by readers who are online. To facilitate online and offline access, future researchers may consider creating the e-storybook in offline mode. Additionally, the current study only developed four topics covered in the first and second semester of grade 4 elementary school. Further research can develop other topics so that the benefits of e-storybooks as supplementary materials can achieve the higher results.

4. CONCLUSION

The developed e-storybooks were expected to be a supplementary material for grade four students in learning English. It was developed based on the Merdeka curriculum and matched to the students' need. By the development of these e-storybooks, students can learn English in the interactive way and more engagement. As the created e-storybooks covered all of four language skills in English learning, it was expected that it helps students to boost their language skills and motivation in learning.

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